
Pest management and control

DISEASES

Bacterial blight found in Africa

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Bacterial blight (BB) of rice, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*, is endemic to Asia and is the most important and damaging bacterial disease of rice. In 1973, BB was reported in northern tropical Australia — the first report from outside Asia. In 1975, it was discovered on and around some rice experiment stations in Colombia and Panama. Although no reports of BB from Africa or Malagasy had been confirmed, there have been

private unconfirmed reports of symptoms resembling those of BB in earlier Taiwanese rice projects in several West African countries on the variety TN1, which was introduced in the 1960s. The senior author searched for the disease in many African countries during the last 4 years but did not detect its presence, even in older rice-growing areas.

In the 1978 growing season, symptoms resembling BB were noted at a rice experiment station at Kogoni, Mali. The authors visited the station in mid-November, at the end of the growing season, and found typical BB symptoms in one block of the variety Gambiaka kokum. Even kresek was found in some plants. Gambiaka kokum is a local tall indica that was grown in large blocks, along with other varieties, for seed distribution. □

Udbatta disease (*Ephelis oryzae*) was observed only in Sarguja district, Bilaspur division, on a local variety in 1969 kharif, and later at Dhamatari block, Raipur district, in 1973 kharif.

Sogatella furcifera is an important rice insect pest in Raipur and Bilaspur regions. About 5% of its adults were found dead with expanded wings on rice plants. Isolations from the dead insects yielded a fungus identified as *Fusarium* sp. Pathogenicity was proved. This may be the first record of this fungus on *S. furcifera* in India. □

Potential of weeds to spread rice tungro in West Bengal, India

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Many graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds can act as symptomless carriers of rice tungro virus disease. An experiment was conducted to determine the potential of weeds to spread tungro in the plant virus experimental rice field at Kalyani, where tungro occurs throughout the year. Virus incidence was surveyed in 1976–77 and 1977–78. The predominant cyperaceous and graminaceous weeds (see table) were brought to the glasshouse and tested for the presence of tungro by indexing the disease incidence on Taichung Native 1 (TN1) seedlings. Virus-free weeds were then inoculated with viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* and tested for virus at 1-month intervals. The percentage of transmission to TN1 seedlings was recorded weekly. Only *Echinochloa colonum* and *Paspalum notatum* transmitted the virus. *E. colonum* infected 16% of the plants, *P. notatum* 20%.

To study the actual potential of the infected weeds to transmit the virus in the field, *E. colonum* plants were grown in pots and inoculated with tungro in

Observations on rice diseases and insects in Madhya Pradesh, India

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Certain observations have been made on rice diseases at Raipur, India.

Rice blast (*Pyricularia oryzae*) is the most important disease in Raipur and Bilaspur divisions, the main rice-growing areas of M.P. Neck blast is usually more important and damaging than leaf blast.

Bacterial blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*) is the next most important disease of cultivated rice. It was first noticed in the area in 1965. In 1970 kharif, blight was observed on *Oryza rufipogon*, a wild rice growing in tanks at Raipur. Brown spot (*Helminthosporium oryzae*), still a minor disease in the area, was also seen on *Oryza rufipogon*.

Bacterial leaf streak (*Xanthomonas translucens* f. sp. *oryzicola*) was first

noticed on a few lines of the cross 34/32 at the rice research farm in 1967. It occurred in epidemic form on IR8 in 1968 kharif. It has also been seen on another wild rice, *Oryza perennis*.

Sheath blight (*Corticium sasakii*) is minor but spreading in the area. During varietal screening, its basidial state was observed in densely growing paddy that was affected by sheath blight.

Stack burn (*Trichoconis padwickii*) is a minor disease, observed only on leaves of semidwarf varieties. In 1972 kharif the following varieties grown in disease screening trials were affected with traces of stack burn while other varieties were free: BCp sp. 1, CR120-181, CR120-182, C24550 (GEB/IR8), C1244(RDR7/TN1), MR89, MR106 (TN1/TKM6), OR10-257 (T90/IR8), R1912 (CO29/IR8), R1922 (CO29/IR8), RP4-12 (T90/IR8), RP4-12 (T90/IR8), RP20-9 (GEB24/Sigadis//IR8), RP175-1, Saturn 587-4 (short culm), Sambalpur E. No. 166, W1251, and No. 6948.0